

Cryogenic Fatigue Strength of Plane Woven Fiber Cloth Reinforced Plastic Laminates and Their Fracture Process

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue characteristics of the fiber reinforced plastics in cryogenic circumstances will become important for designing of structural parts which are used in cold weather countries and of the structures for a super conductive electro-machine which are used in the liquid helium temperature. According to our investigations of research papers on fatigue of F.R.P., however, only a few fatigue experiments on some kinds of F.R.P. had been previously performed in cryogenic circumstances.

Matting and Wagner had first published their studies on the bending fatigue strength of glass/polyester and glass/hydrocarbon laminates at -20°C , in which they all became stronger comparing with those at the room temperature. On the other hand, Tobler and Read reported that the fatigue resistance of unidirectional glass/epoxy laminates at the LHe temperature increased than those at the room temperature. From their S-N diagram, however, one can find that S-N curves at R.T. and LHe temperature gradually close with decreasing of the repeated bending stress, and an intersection by the two S-N curves may be expected at a certain stress level. Shimamura had performed a reversal bending fatigue test at -35°C using the glass chopped strand mat reinforced laminates of polyester and obtained fatigue strength stronger than those at R.T.

It is seemed that different results revealed by those researchers are presumably due to the matrix resin and/or the reinforcing fiber used. The present study aimed to investigate the effect of resin in F.R.P on the fatigue characteristics and to clarify their fatigue fracture process in cryogenic circumstances.

Bending fatigue tests had been done at R.T., -40°C and -80°C by using flat F.R.P. specimens which are made from epoxy, polyester and phenol resin laminates reinforced by the plane woven glass and carbon fiber cloth respectively. Attached figure shows the variations due to cryogenic temperature of tensile and fatigue strength at cycles of 1×10^6 for specimens of various F.R.P. and two kinds of plastics.

The main conclusions are as follows;
The absolute values of fatigue strength in cryogenic circumstances differ

in fact due to their sort of the reinforcements, however, for instance, the values of (fatigue strength of F.R.P.)/(fatigue strength of matrix resin) are independent of the fibers and showed a characteristic variation due to the matrix resin used.

When microscopic crackes in a portion of specimens where the longitudinal and the transversal fiber strands are crossed began to connect to another cracks in a neighbouring crossed portion of fiber strands near the original portion or began to debond in the original portion, the change of temperature (ΔT) and the change in rigidity (ΔEI) of the specimens began to increase remarkably and finally fractured after some number of cycles, which are depend on the repeating stress level.

It was therefore found that the connection to neighbours of cracks or the debondings of the portion where a number of or a few crackes, depending on the resin used, appeared are a sign of the fatigue fracture that will be encountered shortly after.

